

Most Cited Articles In Academia

**International Journal of Web & Semantic
Technology (IJWesT)**

ISSN : 0975 - 9026 (Online) 0976- 2280 (Print)

<http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijwest/ijwest.html>

EVOLUTION OF THE WORLD WIDE WEB : FROM WEB 1.0 TO WEB 4.0

**Sareh Aghaei, Mohammad Ali Nematbakhsh and Hadi Khosravi Farsani,
University of Isfahan, Iran**

ABSTRACT

The World Wide Web as the largest information construct has had much progress since its advent. This paper provides a background of the evolution of the web from web 1.0 to web 4.0. Web 1.0 as a web of information connections, Web 2.0 as a web of people connections, Web 3.0 as a web of knowledge connections and web 4.0 as a web of intelligence connections are described as four generations of the web in the paper.

KEYWORDS

WEB 1.0, WEB 2.0, WEB 3.0, WEB 4.0.

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijwest/papers/3112ijwest01.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijwest/vol3.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Brian, Getting, (2007) “Basic Definitions: Web 1.0, Web 2.0, Web 3.0”, <<http://www.practicalecommerce.com/articles/464-Basic-Definitions-Web-1-0- Web-2-0-Web- 3-0>>.
- [2] Christian, Bizer & Tom, Heath & Tim, Berners-Lee, (2009) “LinkedData-The Story So Far”, Journal Semantic Web and Information Systems.
- [3] W3C,(1999)“ResourceDescriptionFramework(RDF)ModelandSyntaxSpecification”, <<http://www.w3.org/TR/1999/REC-rdf-syntax-19990222/>>.
- [4] SeanB,Palmer,(2001),“TheSemanticWeb:AnIntroduction” <<http://infomesh.net/2001/swintro/>>.
- [5] Ossi,Nykänen(2003),“SemanticWeb:Definition” <<http://www.w3c.tut.fi/talks/2003/0331umediaon/slide6-0.html>>.
- [6] Norasak,Suphakornthanakit(2008),“Web3.0”, <<http://webuser.hs.furtwangen.de/~heindl/ebte-08ssweb-20-Suphakornthanakit.pdf>>. BUILDING AN APPLICATION MODEL AS A SMART SHOP INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY INFRASTRUCTURE AT THE NEIGHBORHOOD LEVEL
- [7] TimBerners-Lee.TheWorldWideWeb:Averyshortpersonalhistory,In: <<http://www.w3.org/People/Berners-Lee/ShortHistory.html>>, 1998
- [8] Christian, Fuchs & Wolfgang, Hofkirchner & Matthias, Schafranek & Celina, Raffl & Marisol, Sandoval & Robert, Bichler (2010), “[Theoretical Foundations of the Web: Cognition, Communication, and Co-Operation. Towards an Understanding of Web 1.0, 2.0, 3.0](#)”, Journal: Future Internets.
- [9] Maged,N.Kamel Boulos&Steve, Wheeler (2007), “[The emerging Web 2.0 social software: an enabling suite of sociable technologies in health and health care education](#)”, Health Information and Libraries Journal, Pp: 2-23.
- [10] San, Murugesan (2007), “Understanding Web 2.0”, Journal IT Professional.
- [11] Jane, Greenberg & Stuart, Sutton & D. Grant, Campbell (2003), “Metadata: A Fundamental Component of the Semantic Web”, Bulletin of the American Society for Information Science and Technology Volume 29, Issue 4, pages 16–18.
- [12] Hamed, Hassanzadeh & MohammadReza, Keyvanpour (2011), “A MACHINE LEARNING BASED ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK FOR SEMANTIC ANNOTATION REQUIREMENTS”.
- [13] Sudhir, Batra (2006), “AJAX-Asynchronous Java Script and XML”, ITS - Information Technology and Systems Management.
- [14] Nova,Spivack(2011),“Web3.0:TheThirdGenerationWebisComing”, <http://lifeboat.com/ex/web.3.0>

- [15] Tim, Berners-Lee & Christian, Bizer & Tom, Heath & Kingsley, Idehen (2008), "Linked Data on the Web", 17th International World Wide Web Conference.
- [16] Oktie, Hassanzadeh (2008), "Introduction to Semantic Web Technologies & Linked Data", <http://www.cs.toronto.edu/~oktie/slides/web-of-data-intro.pdf>
- [17] W3C, (2004), "The Unicode Consortium", <http://www.unicode.org/>.
- [18] Tim, Berners-Lee & James, Hendler & Ora, Lassila (2001), "The Semantic Web", The Scientific American, vol. 5(1).
- [19] Aurore J, Gerber & Andries, Barnard & Aletta Johanna, van der Merwe (2007), "[Towards a semantic web layered architecture](#)", the 25th conference on IASTED International Multi-Conference.
- [20] Mathieu d', Aquin & Enrico, Motta & Marta, Sabou & Sofia, Angeletou & Laurian, Gridinoc & Vanessa, Lopez & Davide, Guidi (2008), "Toward a New Generation of Semantic Web Applications", IEEE Intelligent Systems, 23(3):20-28.
- [21] Hemnath(2010), "Web 4.0-A New Web Technology", <http://websitequality.blogspot.com/2010/01/web-40-new-web-technology.html/>.
- [22] Haytham, Al-Feel & M.A. Koutb & Hoda Suoror (2009), "[Toward An Agreement on Semantic Web Architecture](#)", Proceedings of World Academy of Science, Engineering And Technology Volume 37 January 2009, ISSN 2070-3740.
- [23] Ron, Callari (2009), "Web 4.0, Trip Down the Rabbit Hole or Brave New World?", <http://www.zmogo.com/web/web-40trip-down-the-rabbit-hole-or-brave-new-world/>
- [24] Tim, Berners-Lee & Mark, Fischetti (2000), "Weaving the Web: The Past, Present and Future of the World Wide Web by its Inventor", London, Texere.
- [25] Dan, Farber(2007), "From semantic Web(3.0) to the Web OS(4.0)", <http://www.zdnet.com/blog/btl/from-semantic-web-30-to-the-webos-40/4499/>
- [26] Tim, Berners-Lee(2006), "Linked Data-Design Issues", <http://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html/>.
- [27] Marcus, Cake (2008), "Web 1.0, Web 2.0, Web 3.0 and Web 4.0 explained", <http://www.marcuscake.com/economic-development/internet-evolution/>.
- [28] Tom, Franklin & Mark, van Harmelen (2007), "Web 2.0 for Content for Learning and Teaching in Higher Education", http://www.jisc.ac.uk/media/documents/programmes/digital_repositories/web2-contentlearning-and-teaching.pdf/.
- [29] Alexander, Ritt & Philipp, Hörtler (2008), "Security Aspects in Web 2.0 Mashup Systems", Technology, Altenbergerstrabe 69, 4020 Linz, Austria, http://www.fim.unilinz.ac.at/lva/SE_Netzwerke_und_Sicherheit_Security_Considerations_in_Intercon_Networks/semH.pdf/.

ANT COLONY OPTIMIZATION: A SOLUTION OF LOAD BALANCING IN CLOUD

Ratan Mishra and Anant Jaiswal, Amity school of computer Science, India

ABSTRACT

As the cloud computing is a new style of computing over internet. It has many advantages along with some crucial issues to be resolved in order to improve reliability of cloud environment. These issues are related with the load management, fault tolerance and different security issues in cloud environment. In this paper the main concern is load balancing in cloud computing. The load can be CPU load, memory capacity, delay or network load. Load balancing is the process of distributing the load among various nodes of a distributed system to improve both resource utilization and job response time while also avoiding a situation where some of the nodes are heavily loaded while other nodes are idle or doing very little work. Load balancing ensures that all the processor in the system or every node in the network does approximately the equal amount of work at any instant of time. Many methods to resolve this problem has been came into existence like Particle Swarm Optimization, hash method, genetic algorithms and several scheduling based algorithms are there. In this paper we are proposing a method based on Ant Colony optimization to resolve the problem of load balancing in cloud environment.

KEYWORDS

Cloud computing, Load balance, Ant colony optimization, Swarm intelligence

For More Details : <http://airccse.org/journal/ijwest/papers/3212ijwest03.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijwest/vol3.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Wayne Jansen, Timothy Grance, "Guidelines on Security and Privacy in Public Cloud Computing", National Institute of Standards and Technology Gaithersburg, January 2011.
- [2] Jeep Ruiter, MartijnWarnier, "[Privacy Regulations for Cloud Computing](#)", Faculty of Sciences, VU University Amsterdam
- [3] DanchoDanchev,"Building and Implementing a successful Information Security Policy"
windowsecurity.com- Windows Security Resources for IT admins.
- [4] David Escalante and Andrew J. Korty, Cloud Services: Policy and Assessment, EDUCAUSE Review, vol. 46, no. 4 (July/August 2011)
- [5] Richard N. Katz, "Looking at Clouds from All Sides Now", EDUCAUSE Review, vol. 45, no. 3 (May/June 2010): 32-45
- [6] Anthony T.Velte, Toby J.Velte, Robert Elsenpeter, Cloud Computing A Practical Approach, TATA McGRAW-HILL Edition 2010.
- [7] Martin Randles, David Lamb, A.Taleb-Bendiab,AComparative Study into Distributed Load Balancing Algorithms for Cloud Computing, 2010 IEEE 24th International Conference on Advanced Information Networking and Applications Workshops.
- [8] MladenA.Vouk,CloudComputingIssues,ResearchandImplementations, Proceedings of the ITI 2008 30th Int. Conf. on Information Technology Interfaces, 2008, June 23-26.
- [9] Ali M. Alakeel, A Guide to Dynamic Load Balancing in Distributed Computer Systems, IJCSNS International Journal of Computer Science and Network Security, VOL.10 No.6, June 2010.
- [10] ibm.com/press/us/en/pressrelease/22613.wss
- [11] <http://www.amazon.com/gp/browse.html?node=201590011>
- [12] Martin Randles, EnasOdat, David Lamb, Osama Abu- Rahmeh and A. Taleb-Bendiab, "AComparativeExperimentin Distributed Load Balancing", 2009 Second International Conference on Developments in eSystems Engineering.
- [13] Peter S. Pacheco, "Parallel Programming with MPI", Morgan Kaufmann Publishers Edition 2008
- [14] MequanintMoges, Thomas G.Robertazzi, "[Wireless Sensor Networks: Scheduling for Measurement and Data Reporting](#)", August 31, 2005
- [15] Ali M. Alakeel, [A Guide to Dynamic Load Balancing in Distributed Computer Systems](#),IJCSNS InternationalJournalofComputerScienceandNetwork Security,VOL.10 No.6, June 2010.

- [16] Martin Randles, EnasOdat, David Lamb, Osama Abu- Rahmeh and A. Taleb-Bendiab, "[AComparativeExperiment inDistributed Load Balancing](#)", 2009 Second International Conference on Developments in eSystems Engineering.
- [17] Fourth International Conference on Semantics, Knowledge and Grid" Load Balancing in Nondedicated Grids Using Ant Colony Optimization".
- [18] 9th IEEE/ACMInternationalSymposium on Cluster Computing and the Grid.,2011
- [19] AnthonyT.Velte,TobyJ.Velte,RobertElsenpeter,CloudComputingA PracticalApproach, TATA McGRAW-HILL Edition 2010.

INFERENCE BASED INTERPRETATION OF KEYWORD QUERIES FOR OWL ONTOLOGY

Noman Hasany and Batool Alwatban

Department of Computer Science, College of Computer, Qassim University,
KSA

ABSTRACT

Most of the systems presented to date deals with RDF format so they are limited in actually addressing the knowledge base features from the ontology based on OWL semantics. Now, there is a need that actual OWL features i.e. rules and axioms must be addressed to give precise answers to the user queries. This paper presents an interface to OWL ontology which also considers axioms and restrictions that can result in inferring results in understanding user queries and in selecting appropriate SPARQL queries for getting better interpretation and answers.

KEYWORDS

Keyword query interfaces, OWL axioms, Ontology

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijwest/V8N1/8117ijwest01.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://www.aircse.org/journal/ijwest/vol8.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Kaufmann, Esther, Abraham Bernstein, and Renato Zumstein. "[Querix: A natural language interface to query ontologies based on clarification dialogs.](#)" In 5th International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC 2006), pp. 980-981. 2006.
- [2] Wang, Chong, Miao Xiong, Qi Zhou, and Yong Yu. "[Panto: A portable natural language interface to ontologies.](#)" In European Semantic Web Conference, pp. 473-487. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2007.
- [3] Kaufmann, Esther, Abraham Bernstein, and Lorenz Fischer. "[Nlp-reduce: A “naive” but domainindependent natural language interface for querying ontologies.](#)" 4th ESWC, Innsbruck, A (2007).
- [4] Tran, Thanh, Haofen Wang, Sebastian Rudolph, and Philipp Cimiano. "[Top-k exploration of query candidates for efficient keyword search on graph-shaped \(rdf\) data.](#)" In 2009 IEEE 25th International Conference on Data Engineering, pp. 405-416. IEEE, 2009.
- [5] Hasany, Noman, A. B. Jantan, M. H. B. Selamat, and Mohd Iqbal Saripan. "[Querying ontology using keywords and quantitative restriction phrases.](#)" Inform. Technol. J 9 (2010): 67-78.

- [6] Zhou, Qi, Chong Wang, Miao Xiong, Haofen Wang, and Yong Yu. "[SPARK: adapting keyword query to semantic search.](#)" In The Semantic Web, pp. 694-707. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2007.
- [7] Mäkelä, Eetu. "[Survey of semantic search research.](#)" In Proceedings of the seminar on knowledge management on the semantic web. Department of Computer Science, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, 2005.
- [8] Zenz, Gideon, Xuan Zhou, Enrico Minack, Wolf Siberski, and Wolfgang Nejdl. "[Interactive Query Construction for Keyword Search on the Semantic Web.](#)" In Semantic Search over the Web, pp. 109- 130. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2012.
- [9] Karanastasi, Anastasia, Alexandros Zotos, and Stavros Christodoulakis. "[The OntoNL framework for natural language interface generation and a domain-specific application.](#)" In Digital Libraries: Research and Development, pp. 228-237. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2007.
- [10] KOSSEIM, Leila, Reda SIBLINI, Christopher JO BAKER, and Sabine BERGLER. "[Using Selectional Restrictions to Query an OWL Ontology.](#)"
- [11] Kim, S. I., & Kim, H. S. (2013, January). Ontology modeling for provision of semantic based open API information. In Advanced Communication Technology (ICACT), 2013 15th International Conference on (pp. 664-667). IEEE.
- [12] Kollia, I., Glimm, B., & Horrocks, I. (2011, May). SPARQL query answering over OWL ontologies. In Extended Semantic Web Conference (pp. 382-396). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- [13] Protégé: <http://protege.stanford.edu/>
- [14] Protégé OWL tutorial.
http://mowl-power.cs.man.ac.uk/protegeowltutorial/resources/ProtegeOWLTutorialP3_v1_0.pdf
- [15] Mithun, S., Kosseim, L., & Haarslev, V. (2007, October). [Resolving quantifier and number restriction to question owl ontologies.](#) In Semantics, Knowledge and Grid, Third International Conference on (pp. 218-223). IEEE.
- [16] Schneider, M. (2010, June). SPARQLAS–Implementing SPARQL Queries with OWL Syntax. In Proceedings of the 3rd Workshop on Transforming and Weaving Ontologies in Model Driven Engineering. CEUR Workshop Proceedings (Vol. 604).

SELECTION MECHANISM OF MICRO-SERVICES ORCHESTRATION VS. CHOREOGRAPHY

Neha Singhal¹, Usha Sakthivel¹, Pethuru Raj²

¹Department of Information Science and Engineering, Rajarajeswari College of Engineering, Bangalore, INDIA

²Reliance Jio Infocomm. Ltd (RJIL), SARGOD imperial, 23, Residency Road Bangalore, INDIA

ABSTRACT

Web services is a special case of a service-oriented architecture (SOA), which is, basically, a representation of web application's functionality. Web service is more of a generalized concept that implies whole functionality as a whole but Microservice handles only the single specific task. MSA is emerging as an excellent architecture style enabling the division of large and complex applications into micro-scale yet many services, each runs in its own process, has its own APIs, and communicates with one another using lightweight mechanisms such as HTTP. Microservices are built around business capabilities, loosely coupled and highly cohesive, horizontally scalable, independently deployable, technology-agnostic, etc. On the other side for the business dynamic requirement these microservices need to be composed for the realization of enterprise-scale, and business-critical applications. Service composition is combining various services together to provide the solution for the user dynamic queries. There are two methods for the microservice composition i.e. orchestration and choreography. In this paper, a health case study is performed for the selection mechanism of orchestration method and choreography method in various situation.

KEYWORDS

MSA, Composition of services, SOA.

For More Details : <http://airconline.com/ijwest/V10N1/10119ijwest01.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijwest/vol10.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Damian Arellanes , Kung-Kiu Lau” [D-XMAN: A Platform For Total Compositionality in ServiceOriented Architectures](#)” 2017 IEEE 7th International Symposium on Cloud and Service Computing DOI 10.1109/SC2.2017.55
- [2] Kleantlis Thramboulidis, Danai C. Vachtsevanou, Alexandros Solanos” [Cyber-Physical Microservices An IoT-based Framework for Manufacturing Systems](#)” 2018 IEEE .
- [3] Damian Arellanes and Kung-Kiu Lau” [Exogenous Connectors for Hierarchical Service Composition](#)” 2017IEEE 10th International Conference on Service-Oriented Computing and Applications” DOI 10.1109/SOCA.2017.25
- [4] Chris peltz“web service orchistration and choreography” IEEE Computer society,2003.
- [5] Festim Halili,Eip Rufati , Iliia Ninka “[Styles of Service Composition – Analysis and Comparison Methods](#) ” 2013 Fifth International Conference on Computational Intelligence, Communication Systems and Networks.
- [6] Tanveer Ahmed, Abhishek Srivastava “[Service Choreography: Present and Future](#)” 2014 IEEE International Conference on Services Computing DOI 10.1109/SCC.2014.126.
- [7] Sirine Rebai, Hatem Hadj Kacem, Mohamed Kar^aa , Saul E. Pomares and Ahmed Hadj Kacem1,” A Service-Oriented Architecture (SOA) Framework for Choreography Verification” IEEE, ICIS 2015, June 28-July 1 2015, Las Vegas, USA 978-1-4799-8679-8
- [8] Junio C. Lima Ricardo C. A. Rocha , Fabio M. Costa,” An Approach for QoS-Aware Selection of Shared Services for Multiple Service Choreographies” 2016 IEEE Symposium on Service-Oriented System Engineering.
- [9] Ján Terpák, Pavel Horovák, Matej Luká,” Mathematical models creation using orchestration and choreography of web services” 2016 IEEE 978-1-4673-8606-7.
- [10] Nacera Temgli,Abdelghani Chibani, Karim Djouani, and Mohamed Ahmed Nacer,” A Distributed Agent-Based Approach for Optimal QoS Selection in Web of Object Choreography” IEEE SYSTEMS JOURNAL, VOL. 12, NO. 2, JUNE 2018, 1937-9234
- [11] Lei Chen* and Cristofer Englund,” Choreographing services for smart cities: smart traffic demonstration” 2017 IEEE 978-1-5090-5932-4.

- [12] UrjitaThakar, AmitTiwari, SudarshanVarma “Choreography-based vs Orchestration-based Servic Composition in Opportunistic Networks” 2017 IEEE 13th International Conference on Wireless and Mobile Computing, Networking and Communications (WiMob)
- [13] Shang-Pin Ma*, Peng-Zhong Chen, Yang-Sheng Ma, and Jheng-ShiunJiang“CARSB Portal: A WebBased Software Tool to Composing Service Bricks and RESTful Services as Mobile Apps” 978-1- 5090-3438-3/16 2016 IEEE DOI 10.1109/ICS.2016.118
- [14] Shang-Pin Ma, Ci-Wei Lan, Ching-Ting Ho, and Jiun-Hau Ye,” QoS-Aware Selection of Web APIs Based on _Pareto Genetic Algorithm” 978-1-5090-3438-3/16 2016 IEEE DOI 10.1109/ICS.2016.121
- [15] Youngmee Shin, Wanki Park, Ilwoo Lee,” Design of Microgrid Web Services for Microgrid Applications” 978-1-5090-4749-9/17IEEE ICUFN 2017
- [16] Elyas Ben HadjYahia; Laurent R_veill_ere, Y_erom-David Bromberg, Raphael Chevalier, and Alain Cadot,” [Medley: An Event-Driven Lightweight Platform For Service Composition](#)”
- [17] Martin Garriga , CristianMateos , AndresFlores , AlejandraCechich , Alejandro Zunino “[RESTful service composition at a glance: A survey](#)” Journal of Network and Computer Applications (2016)
- [18] Bhaskar Kapoor¹ and Savita Sharma²” [A Comparative Study Ontology Building Tools for Semantic Web Applications](#)”
- [19] H. H. Kian¹ and M. Zahedi²” [AN EFFICIENT APPROACH FOR KEYWORD SELECTION; IMPROVING ACCESSIBILITY OF WEB CONTENTS BY GENERAL SEARCH ENGINES](#)”
- [20] Q. Z. Sheng, X. Qiao, A. V. Vasilakos, C. Szabo, S. Bourne, and X. Xu, “[Web services composition: A decade’s overview](#),” Information Sciences, vol. 280, pp. 218–238, Oct. 2014.

CONFIGURING ASSOCIATIONS TO INCREASE TRUST IN PRODUCT PURCHASE

Pegah Moslemipoor¹ and Ali Haroon Abadi²

¹Department of Computer Engineering, Kish International Branch, Islamic Azad University, Kish, Iran

²Department of Computer Engineering, Islamic Azad University, Science and Research Branch, Tehran, Iran

ABSTRACT

Clustering is categorizing data into groups with similar objects. Data mining adds to complexities of clustering a large dataset with various features. Among these datasets, there are electronic business stores which offer their products through web. These stores require recommendation systems which can offer products to the user which the user might require them with higher probability. In this study, previous purchases of users are used to present a sorted list of products to the user. Identifying associations related to users and finding centers increases precision of the recommended list. Configuration of associations and creating a profile for users is important in current studies. In the proposed method, association rules are presented to model user interactions in the web which use time that a page is visited and frequency of visiting a page to weight pages and describes users' interest to page groups. Therefore, weight of each transaction item describes user's interest in that item. Analyzing results show that the proposed method presents a more complete model of users' behavior because it combines weight and membership degree of pages simultaneously for ranking candidate pages. This method has obtained higher accuracy compared to other methods even in higher number of pages.

KEYWORDS

Data mining, association rule, clustering, previous behavior of user, recommender system

For More Details : <http://airconline.com/ijwest/V9N3/9318ijwest04.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijwest/vol9.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Yeh, I., & Lien, C. (2008). [The comparisons of data mining techniques for the predictive accuracy of probability of default of credit card clients](#), Expert Systems with Applications 36 (2) (2008) 2473–2480.
- [2] Castellón González, Pamela, and Juan D. Velásquez., (2013), "[Characterization and detection of taxpayers with false invoices using data mining techniques](#)."Expert Systems with Applications 40.5 (2013): 1427-1436.
- [3] Richa Gupta ,(2014),“Journey from Data Mining to Web Mining to Big Data”, International Journal of Computer Trends and Technology (IJCTT) ,page 18-20, volume 10 number 1 , Apr 2014.
- [4] <http://academic.csuohio.edu/fuy/Pub/pot97.pdf>
- [5] Mansi Gera, Shivani Goel, (2015), [Data Mining - Techniques, Methods and Algorithms: A Review on Tools and their Validity](#), International Journal of Computer Applications (0975 – 8887) Volume 113 – No. 18, March 2015, pages 22-29.
- [6] M. Sinthuja, N. Puviarasan and P. Aruna, (2017), [Evaluating the Performance of Association Rule Mining Algorithms](#), World Applied Sciences Journal 35 (1): 43-53, 2017.
- [7] E. W. T. Ngai, “[Customer relationship management research \(1992-2002\): An academicleterature review and classification](#),” Mark. Intell. Plan., vol. 23, no. 6, pp. 582–605, Jan.2005.
- [8] K.Karthikeyan and Dr.V.Karthikeyani, (2014), [Association Rule Mining Based Extraction of Semantic Relations Using Markov Logic Network](#),
- [9] Hoda Khanali, Babak Vaziri, (2017), [A Survey on Improved Algorithms for Mining Association Rules](#), International Journal of Computer Applications (0975 – 8887) Volume 165 – No.9, May 2017, pages:6-11.
- [10] Amuit Kumar Chandan, Kavita & M K Shukla, ,(2017), [ASSOCIATION RULE MINING USING MODIFIED BPSO](#), International Journal of Computer Science Engineering and Information Technology Research (IJCSEITR) ISSN(P): 2249-6831; ISSN(E): 2249-7943 Vol. 7, Issue 2, Apr 2017, 29-36.
- [11] Rekha Jain , Dr. G. N. Purohit, (2011), "[Page Ranking Algorithms for Web Mining](#)” , International Journal of Computer Applications (0975 – 8887) Volume 13– No.5, January 2011.

- [12] K. S. Ranjith, Yang Zhenning, Ronnie D. Caytiles and N. Ch. S. N. Iyengar,(2017) ,[Comparative Analysis of Association Rule Mining Algorithms for the Distributed Data](#), International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology Vol.102 (2017), pp.49-60.
- [13] MS.J.OMANA, MS.S.MONIKA, MS.B.DEEPIKA, (2017), [SURVEY ON EFFICIENCY OF ASSOCIATION RULE MINING TECHNIQUES](#), J.OMANA et al, International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing, Vol.6 Issue.4, April- 2017, pg. 5-8.
- [14] Prachi Surwade1, Prof. Satish S. Banait, (2016), [A Survey On Clustering Techniques For Mining Big Data](#), International Journal of Advanced Research in Science Management and Technology, Volume 2, Issue 2, February 2016.
- [15] T. Sajana, C. M. Sheela Rani and K. V. Narayana , (2016), [A Survey on Clustering Techniques for Big Data Mining](#), Indian Journal of Science and Technology, Vol 9(3), January 2016.
- [16] Barkha Narang, Poonam Verma, Priya Kochar, (2016), [Application based, advantageous K-means Clustering Algorithm in Data Mining – A Review](#), International Journal of Latest Trends in Engineering and Technology (IJLTET), ISSN: 2278-621X Vol 7 issue 2 July 2016.
- [17] Rahul Singh, Kanika chuchra and Akshama Rani, (2017), [A Survey on the Generation o Recommender Systems](#), I.J. Information Engineering and Electronic Business, 2017, 3, 26-35 Published Online May 2017.
- [18] Debashis Das, Laxman Sahoo, Sujoy Datta ,(2017) , [A Survey on Recommendation System](#), International Journal of Computer Applications (0975 – 8887) Volume 160 – No 7, February 2017.
- [19] Kwek Choon Ling (Corresponding author) , [The Effects of Shopping Orientations, Online Trust and Prior Online Purchase Experience toward Customers’ Online Purchase Intention](#) , International Business Research , ISSN 1913-9004 ,pp.63-76,Vol. 3, No. 3; July 2010.

IDENTIFYING IMPORTANT FEATURES OF USERS TO IMPROVE PAGE RANKING ALGORITHMS

Amir Hossein Eskandari¹ and Ali Haroun Abadi²

¹Department of Computer Engineering, Kish International Branch, Islamic Azad University, Kish, Iran

²Department of Computer Engineering, Islamic Azad University, Science and Research Branch, Tehran, Iran

ABSTRACT

Web is a wide, various and dynamic environment in which different users publish their documents. Webmining is one of data mining applications in which web patterns are explored. Studies on web mining can be categorized into three classes: application mining, content mining and structure mining. Today, internet has found an increasing significance. Search engines are considered as an important tool to respond users' interactions. Among algorithms which is used to find pages desired by users is page rank algorithm which ranks pages based on users' interests. However, as being the most widely used algorithm by search engines including Google, this algorithm has proved its eligibility compared to similar algorithm, but considering growth speed of Internet and increase in using this technology, improving performance of this algorithm is considered as one of the web mining necessities. Current study emphasizes on Ant Colony algorithm and marks most visited links based on higher amount of pheromone. Results of the proposed algorithm indicate high accuracy of this method compared to previous methods. Ant Colony Algorithm as one of the swarm intelligence algorithms inspired by social behavior of ants can be effective in modeling social behavior of web users. In addition, application mining and structure mining techniques can be used simultaneously to improve page ranking performance.

KEYWORDS

web mining, application mining, web page ranking, page rank algorithm, ant colony algorithm

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijwest/V9N3/9318ijwest03.pdf>

Volume Link : <http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijwest/vol9.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Seema Rani , Upasana Garg,(2014), “[A Ranking Of Web Documents Using Semantic Similarity And Artificial Intelligence Based Search Engine](#)”, International Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology Research (IJSETR), Volume 3, Issue 12, ISSN: 2278 – 7798 ,page 3354-3357.
- [2] Nisha , Dr. Paramjeet singh, (July 2014) ,“[A Review Paper on SEO based Ranking of Web Documents](#) “,International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering, Volume 4, Issue 7, ISSN: 2277 128X, page1136-1140 .
- [3] Hee-Gook Jun, Dong-Hyuk Im, and Hyoung-Joo Kim, (2016),[An RDF metadata-based weighted semantic pageRank algorithm](#), International Journal of Web & Semantic Technology (IJWesT) Vol.7, No.2, pages:11-24.
- [4] Pranit B. Mohata,(April 2015) ,“[Web Data Mining Techniques and Implementation for Handling Big Data](#)”, International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing , ISSN 2320–088X, Vol. 4, Issue. 4, pg.330– 334.
- [5] Perna Rai, Arvind Lal,(2016), “ [Google PageRank Algorithm: Markov Chain Model and Hidden Markov Model](#)” , International Journal of Computer Applications (0975 – 8887) Volume 138 – No.9, March 2016, pages:9-13.
- [6] M. Sathya, Dr. P. Isakki, (2017), “ [Eclat Algorithm on Web Log Data for Mining the Frequent Link](#)”, International Journal of Innovative Research in Computer and Communication Engineering, Vol. 5, Special Issue 1, March 2017, pages:85-92.
- [7] Abha Joshi , Avani Jadeja ,(May, 2015) , “[Improving Algorithm for Calculation of Page Rank](#) ” , The International Journal Of Science & Technoledge (ISSN 2321 – 919X) , , pages 23-25.
- [8] Rekha Jain , Dr. G. N. Purohit,(2011), "[Page Ranking Algorithms for Web Mining](#)” , International Journal of Computer Applications (0975 – 8887) Volume 13– No.5.
- [9] Phyu Thwe,(2013) ,” [Proposed Approach For Web Page Access Prediction Using Popularity And Similarity Based Page Rank Algorithm](#) “,International Journal of Scientific & Technology, ISSN 2277-8616 ,pages 240-246.
- [10] A.M. Sote , S. R. Pande,(2014) , “[Application of Page Ranking Algorithm in Web Mining](#)”, International Conference on Advances in Engineering & Technology , IOSR Journal of Computer Science (IOSR-JCE) , p-ISSN: 2278-8727 ,Pages 47-51.

- [11] M. Dorigo and G. Di Caro, (1999), "[The ant colony optimization meta-heuristic](#)" In: New Ideas in Optimization, D. Corne, M. Dorigo and F.Glover Eds. London, UK: McGraw Hill, pp. 11-32.
- [12] Moghimi. M, Zare, R and Noruzi, Sima,(2016), A hybrid method for preprocessing a web server record file, third International Conference on Applied Research in Computer Science and Information Technology,
- [13] M. Dorigo and G. Di Caro, (1999), "[The ant colony optimization meta-heuristic](#)" In: New Ideas in Optimization, D. Corne, M. Dorigo and F.Glover Eds. London, UK: McGraw Hill, pp. 11-32.
- [14] K. Etmnani and M. Akbarzadeh-T and N. Raeji Yanehsari,(2009), "[Web Usage Mining: users', navigational patterns extraction from web logs,](#)" IFSA-EUSFLAT, pp. 396-401.
- [15] H.Hannah Inbarani and K. Thangavel and A. Pethalakshmi, (2007), "[Rough set based Feature Selection for Web Usage Mining,](#)" Conference on Computational Intelligence and Multimedia Applications, Vol 1, pp. 33-38.

AUTOMATIC CONVERSION OF RELATIONAL DATABASES INTO ONTOLOGIES: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF PROTÉGÉ PLUG-INS PERFORMANCES

Kgotatso Desmond Mogotlane¹ and Jean Vincent Fonou-Dombeu²

¹The South African Mint Company, Pretoria, South Africa

²Department of Software Studies, Vaal University of Technology, Vanderbijlpark, South Africa

ABSTRACT

Constructing ontologies from relational databases is an active research topic in the Semantic Web domain. While conceptual mapping rules/principles of relational databases and ontology structures are being proposed, several software modules or plug-ins are being developed to enable the automatic conversion of relational databases into ontologies. However, the correlation between the resulting ontologies built automatically with plug-ins from relational databases and the database-toontology mapping principles has been given little attention. This study reviews and applies two Protégé plug-ins, namely, DataMaster and OntoBase to automatically construct ontologies from a relational database. The resulting ontologies are further analysed to match their structures against the database-to-ontology mapping principles. A comparative analysis of the matching results reveals that OntoBase outperforms DataMaster in applying the database-to-ontology mapping principles for automatically converting relational databases into ontologies.

KEYWORDS

Relational Database, Ontology, Sematic Web, Protégé Plug-in, Database-to-Ontology Mapping Principles.

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijwest/V7N4/7416ijwest03.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijwest/vol7.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Hu W. and Qu Y., "[Discovering Simple Mappings Between Relational Database Schemas and Ontologies](#)," in Proc. 6th International Semantic Web Conference, Busan, Korea, pp. 225-238, 2007.
- [2] Gherabi N., Addakiri K. and Bahaj M., "[Mapping relational database into OWL Structure with data semantic preservation](#)," International Journal of Computer Science and Information Security, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 42-47, 2012.
- [3] Cristani M. and Cuel R., "[A Comprehensive Guideline for Building a Domain Ontology from Scratch](#)," in Proc. WWW 2012 - Session: Ontology Representation and Querying: RDF and SPARQL, Graz, Austria, pp.205- 212, 2004.
- [4] Madhu G., Govardhan A. and Rajinikanth T.V., "[Intelligent Semantic Web Search Engines: A Brief Survey](#)," International Journal of Web & Semantic Technology (IJWesT), vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 34-42, 2011.
- [5] Imandi N. and Rizvi S.A.M., "[An Approach to OWL Concept Extraction and Integration across Multiple Ontologies](#)," International Journal of Web & Semantic Technology (IJWesT), vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 33-51, 2012.
- [6] Spanos D., Stravrou P. and Mitrou N., "[Bringing Relational Databases into the Semantic Web: A Survey](#)," Semantic Web Journal, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 169-209, 2012.
- [7] Sequeda J.F., Marcelo A. and Miranker D.P., "[On Directly Mapping Rational Databases to RDF and OWL](#)," in Proc. WWW 2012 - Session: Ontology Representation and Querying: RDF and SPARQL, Lyon, France, pp.649-658, 2012.
- [8] Tirmizi S.H., Sequeda J. and Miranker D., "[Translating SQL Applications to the Semantic Web](#)," in Proc.19th International Conference on Database and Expert Systems (DEXA 2008),Turin, Italy, pp. 450-464,2008.
- [9] Li M., Du X. and Wang S., "[Learning Ontology from Relational Database](#)," in Proc. Fourth International Conference on Machine Learning and Cybernetics, Guangzhou, China, pp. 3410-3415, 2005.
- [10] Jain V. and Singh M., "[A framework to Convert Relational Database to Ontology For Knowledge Database in Semantic Web](#)," International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research, vol. 2, no. 10, pp. 9-12, 2013.
- [11] Pasha M. and Sattar A., "[Building Domain Ontologies From Relational Database Using Mapping Rules](#)," International Journal of Intelligent Engineering & Systems, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 20-27, 2013.
- [12] Zhou S., Ling H., Han M. and Zhang H., "[Ontology Generator from Rational Database on Jena](#)," Computer and Information Science Technology, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 263-267, 2010.
- [13] Cerbah F., "[Learning highly structured semantic repositories from relational database: The](#)

- [RDBToOnto tool](#),” in Proc. 5th Annual European Semantic Web Conference (ESWS 2008), Tenerife, Canary Islands, Spain, Jun 2008.
- [14] Alatrish E.S., “[Comparison of Ontology Editors](#),” eRAF Journal on Computing, Vol. 4, pp. 23-38, 2012.
- [15] Buitelaar P., Olejnik D. and Sintek M., “[A Protégé Plug-in for Ontology Extraction from Text Based on Linguistic Analysis](#),” in Proc. 1st European Semantic Web Symposium (ESWS 2004), Heraklion, Greece, May 2004.
- [16] Mulligann C., Trame J. and Krzysztof J., “[Introducing the new SIMDLA Semantic Similarity Measurement Plug-in for the Protégé Ontology Editor](#),” in Proc. 1st ACM SIGSPATIAL International Workshop on Spatial Semantics and Ontologies, Chicago, USA, Nov 2011.
- [17] Nyulas C., O’Connor M. and Tu S., “[DataMaster - a Plug-in for Importing Schemas and Data from Relational Databases into Protégé](#),” in Proc. 10th International Protg Conference, Budapest, Hungary, pp. 15-18, 2007.
- [18] DataGenie. Available at: <http://protege.cim3.net/cgi-bin/wiki.pl?DataGenie> [Accessed 10.10.2015].
- [19] OntoBase. Available at: <http://code.google.com/p/ontobase/>; <http://protegewiki.stanford.edu/wiki/OntoBase> [Accessed 11.10.2015].
- [20] Papapanagiotou P., Katsioulis P., Tsetsos V., Anagnostopoulos C. and Hadjiefthymiades S., “RONGO: Relational to Ontology Schema Matching,” AIS SIGSEMIS Bulletin, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 32-36, 2006.
- [21] Cullot N., Ghawi R. and Ytongnon K., “[DB2OWL: A Tool for Automatic Database-to-Ontology Mapping](#),” in: Michelangelo Ceci; Donato Malerba & Letizia Tanca, ed. ‘SEBD’, pp. 491-494, 2007.
- [22] Telnarova Z., “Relational database as a source of ontology creation,” in Proc. International Multiconference on Computer Science and Information Technology, Wisla, Poland, pp. 135-139, 2010.
- [23] Sedighi S.M. and Javidan R., “[Semantic query in a relational database using local ontology construction](#),” South African Journal of Science, vol. 108, no. 11/12, pp. 1-10, 2012.
- [24] Zhang L. and Li K., “[Automatic Generation of Ontology Based on Database](#),” Journal of Computational Information Systems, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 1148-1154, 2011.
- [25] Cerbah F., “Mining the Content of Relational Databases to Learn Ontologies with Deeper Taxonomies,” in Proc. IEEE/WIC/ACM International Joint Conference on Web Intelligence (WI’08) and Intelligent Agent Technology (IAT’08), Sydney, Australia, pp. 553-557, 2008.
- [26] Transitioning Applications to Ontology, RDBToOnto: From Relational Databases to Ontologies. Available at: <http://www.taoproject.eu/researchanddevelopment/demosanddownloads/RDBToOnto.html>

[Accessed 11.10.2015].

- [27] Navathe S.B., "[Evolution of Data Modelling for Databases](#)," Communications of the ACM, vol. 35, no. 9, pp.112-123, 1992.
- [28] Mahmood N., Burney A. and Ahsan K., "[A logical Temporal Relational Model](#)," International Journal of Computer Science Issues, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 1-9, 2010.
- [29] Saleh M.E., "[Semantic-Based Query in Relational Database using Ontology](#)," Canadian Journal on Data,Information and Knowledge Engineering, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 1-16, 2011.
- [30] Jia C. and Yue W., "[Rules-based object-relational databases ontology construction](#)," Journal of Systems Engineering and Electronics, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 211-215, 2009.
- [31] Lemaignan S., Siadat A., Dantan J. and Semenenko A., "[MASON: A Proposal for an Ontology of Manufacturing Domain](#)," In the Proceedings of the IEEE Workshop on Distributed Intelligent Systems:Collective Intelligence and its Applications, Prague, Czech Republic, 2006.
- [32] Authors, Published Manuscript.
- [33] OWLViz. Available at: <http://protegewiki.stanford.edu/wiki/OWLViz> [Accessed 20.10.2015].
- [34] OntoGraf. Available at: <http://protegewiki.stanford.edu/wiki/OntoGraf> [Accessed 20.10.2015].
- [35] Parrot: A RIF and OWL documentation service. Available at: <http://ontorule-project.eu/parrot/parrot> [Accessed 20.10.2015].

SEMANTIC DATA INTEGRATION APPROACHES FOR E-GOVERNANCE

Dr. Mohammed T. Al-Sudairy¹ and T. G. K Vasista²

¹College of Business Administration, King Saud University, Riyadh, KSA

²King Saud University, Riyadh, KSA

ABSTRACT

Increased generation of data in the e-governance R&D process is required to generate the expected services in terms of enhanced e-services productivity and pipelines. The inability of existing integration strategies to organise and apply the available knowledge to the range of real scientific, business and governance issues is impacting on not only productivity but also transparency of information in crucial safety and regulatory applications. This requires focusing on normative models of e-governance that typically can assert horizontal (inter-agency) and vertical (inter-governmental) integration of data flows to represent the most sophisticated form of e-government delivering greatest payoff for both governments and users. The new range of semantic technologies based on ontology enable proper integration of knowledge in a way that is reusable by several applications across governance business from discovery to ministry affairs. The objective of this paper is to provide an insight on the necessary and sufficient knowledge base to deal with data integration using semantic web technologies applicable for e-governance based on exploratory research using literature survey. It assumes that reader has the capability of understanding some basic knowledge on E-governance, Relational Database Management, Ontology, and Service Oriented Architecture and Semantic Web Technology.

KEYWORDS

Data Integration, E-Government, Ontologies, Semantic Web, Semantic Data Integration.

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijwest/papers/0111ijwest01.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijwest/vol2.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Farooq M. K., Shamail S., Awais M. M. (2008) "[Devolution in a Virtual Enterprise: Pervasive Collaborative Network](#)", IFIP International Federation for Information Processing, Volume 283/2008, 433-440.
- [2] Peters R. M., Janssen M., Engers T. M. van (2004) "[Measuring e-Government Impact: Existing practices and shortcomings](#)", In Marijn Janssen, Henk G. Sol, and René W. Wagenaar (Eds.), ICEC'04, Sixth International Conference on Electronic Commerce, ACM
- [3] Marche S and McNiven J D (2003) "[E-Government and E-Governance: The future isn't what it used to be](#)" Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences, Vol. 20, No. 1, pp 74-86.
- [4] International Centre for E-Governance, International Centre of e-governance from the Scottish Council Foundation, www.icegov.org
- [5] Singh G. Pathak R. D. Naz R. (2010) "[Service Delivery Through E-Governance: Perception and Expectations of Customers in Fiji and PNG](#)", Public Organization Review, 1566-7170, pp 1-14, Springer Science+Business Media, LLC
- [6] Kieler (2008) "[Semantic Data Integration across Different Scales: Automatic Learning of Generalization Rules](#)", The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences. Vol. XXXVII. Part B2. Beijing 2008
- [7] Santoso H. A., Abdul-Mehdi Z. T., Haw S. (2009) "[Semantic Enhancement Framework for eGovernment Using Ontology Versioning Approach](#)", The 6th International Conference on Information Technology and Applications (ICITA 9-12-, Nov. 2009), Hanoi, Vietnam, ISBN:978-981-08-3029-8.
- [8] Elmagarmid A K, McIver W J. (2001). "[Guest Editors Introduction: The Ongoing March towards Digital Government](#)", Computer, Vol. 34, No. 2, pp 32-38.
- [9] Medjahed B, Rezgui A., Bouguettaya Athman and Ouzzani Mourad (2003) "[Infrastructure for e-Government Web Services](#)", IEEE Internet
- [10] Huhns M. N. and Singh M. P (2005) "[Service Oriented Computing: Key Concepts and Principles](#)", IEEE Internet Computing, vol. 09, No. 1.
- [11] Hodgson R, Allemang D, Chpater-3: Semantic Technology for E-Government, Top Quadrant Inc. Retrieved as pdf via WWW on Nov 2, 2010.
- [12] Federal Enterprise Architecture (2004), <http://www.feapmo.gov/>
- [13] Klischewski, R., Ukena, S., (2007) "[Designing semantic e-Government services driven by user requirements, in: Electronic Government](#)", 6th International EGOV Conference, Proceedings of ongoing research, project Contributions and workshops, Trauner Verlag, Linz, pp. 133-140.
- [14] D'Urso Ciro (2003) "Toward a Cooperative Architecture for Delivering Government

- Services”, Part 1, IT Professional, Vol. 05, No. 6 pp 61-63, 64
- [15] D’Urso Ciro (2004) “Toward a Cooperative Architecture for Delivering Government Services” Part 2, IT Professional, Vol. 05, No. 6 pp 61-63, 64
- [16] Mecella M, Batini C (2001) “[Enabling Italian e-Government through a Cooperative Architecture](#)”, Computer, Vol. 34, No.2, pp61-63, 64.
- [17] Peltz Chris (2003) “[Web Services Orchestration and Choreography](#)”, Computer, Vol. 36, No.10, pp 46-52.
- [18] Furdiki K, Klischewski R, Paralic M, Sabol T, Skokan M (2010) E-Government Service Integration and Provision Using Semantic Technologies, retrieved on Nov. 2, 2010 via WWW @ http://web.tuke.sk/fei-cit/furdik/publik/egov09_aeg.pdf
- [19] Commission of the European Communities, COM (2006) “[Interoperability for Pan-European e-Government Services](#)”. 45 final, Brussels. Computing, Vol. 07, No. 1, pp 58-65
- [20] Halevy, Rajaramn, Ordille (2006) “[Data Integration: The Teenage Years](#)”, VLDB ‘06, September 12-15, Seoul, Korea, ACM.
- [21] Lacroix Z and Crichlow T (2003), Bioinformatics: Managing Scientific Data, Morgan Kaufman
- [22] Lenzerini M (2002) “[Data Integration: A Theoretical Perspective](#)”, Proceedings of the Symposium on Principles of Database Systems (PODS), pp233-246
- [23] Hull R (1997) “[Managing Semantic heterogeneity in databases: A theoretical perspective](#)” In proceedings of 16th ACM SIGACT SIGMOD SIGART Symposium. On Principles of Database Systems.
- [24] Ullman J D (1997) “[Information Integration using logical views](#)” In In Proc. of the 6th Int. Conf. on Database Theory (ICDT’97), volume 1186 of Lecture Notes in Computer Science, pages 19–40. Springer, 1997
- [25] Anwar N, Huntz E, Kolch W, Pitti A, (2010) “Semantic Data Integration for Francisella tularensis novicida Proteomic and Genomic Data”; retrieved on Nov. 2, 2010 from WWW @ www.cis.strath.ac.uk/~ela/AnwarSWAT4LS_5.pdf
- [26] Gardner S. P. (2005) “[Ontologies and Semantic Data Integration](#)”, Drug Discovery Today, Vol. 10, Issue 14, p1001-1007
- [27] Apostolou D, Stojanovic L, Lobo T P and Thoenssen B (2005) “[Towards a Semantically Driven Software Engineering Environment for eGovernment](#)”, in M. Böhlen et al. (Eds.): TCGOV 2005, LNAI 3416, pp. 157 –168, IFIP International Federation for Information Processing 2005.
- [28] Lehti P, Frankhauser P (2004) “[XML Data Integration with OWL: Experiences and Challenges](#)”, Proceedings of International Symposium on Applications and the Internet, Tokyo, Japan.

- [29] Oracle, Semantic Data Integration for the Enterprise - Oracle Semantic Technologie, retrieved on Nov 3, 2010 from WWW available @ <http://www.semanticuniverse.com/articlessemantic-data-integration-enterprise-oracle-semantic-technologies.html>
- [30] He B, Patel M, Zgang Z and Chuan Chang K (2007) “Accessing the Deep Web”, Communications of the ACM - ACM at sixty: a look back in time, Volume 50 Issue 5, Magazine, May 2007.
- [31] Juansequeda blog (2010) Semantic Web in Austin available @ <http://www.semanticuniverse.com/blogs-relational-database-and-semantic-web.html> and also available at http://semanticweb.com/relational-database-and-the-semantic-web_b16083
- [32] Wiki-Triplestore, Triplestore @ <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Triplestore>
- [33] Microyannidis A., Theodoolidis B. (2010) “Ontology management and evolution for business intelligence”, International Journal of Information Management, Volume 30, Issue 6, December 2010, Pages 559-566
- [34] Hartig, Bizer and Fratag (2009) Executing SPARQL Queries over the Web of Linked Data, International Semantic Web Conference (ISWC2009), available as a raw reference @ <http://data.semanticweb.org/conference/iswc/2009/paper/research/301/html>.
- [35] SQUIN (2010) @ <http://squ.in.sourceforge.net/>
- [36] Feigenbaum Lee (2008), SPARQL by Example, <http://www.cambridge semantics.com>
- [37] McCarthy Philip (2004), Introduction to Jena: Use RDF models in your Java applications with the Jena Semantic Web Framework, www.ibm.com
- [38] Colomo-Palacio R., Garcia-Crespo A. and Soto-Acosta P., (2010) “[A case analysis of semantic technologies for R&D intermediation information management](#)”, International Journal of Information Management 30 (2010) 465–469.
- [39] Vasista T. G. K. (2008) “Innovative Role of Broadband as an ICT promoter for Improving Economy and Reducing Poverty in Nepal”, Proceedings of the International conference on Electronic Commerce in the 21st Century (ECIC-2008), 2-4 June 2008, Khatmandu, Nepal, pp. 179-187.
- [40] IndiaPoliticalBlog.Com, <http://indiapoliticalblog.com/2010/11/10/the-strange-case-of-the-telecom-minister-a-raj-a-who-is-accused-of-incredible-corruption-in-telecom/>
- [41] Miller R., Glen Jack; Jaspersen Fred; Karmokolias Yannis (1997) “International Joint Ventures in Developing Countries”, Finance & Development / March 1997, pp 26-29.
- [42] Chen Z, Gangopadhyay A, Holden S, Karabatis G, McGuire M (2007) “[Semantic integration of government data for water quality management](#)”, Government Information Quarterly ,24, 716–735.

AUTOMATICALLY CONVERTING TABULAR DATA TO RDF: AN ONTOLOGICAL APPROACH

Kumar Sharma¹, Ujjal Marjit^{2*}, and Utpal Biswas³

¹Department of Computer Science and Engineering, University of Kalyani, Kalyani,
West Bengal, India

²Center for Information Resource Management (CIRM), University of Kalyani,
Kalyani, West Bengal, India

³Department of Computer Science and Engineering, University of Kalyani, Kalyani,
West Bengal, India

ABSTRACT

Information residing in relational databases and delimited file systems are inadequate for reuse and sharing over the web. These file systems do not adhere to commonly set principles for maintaining data harmony. Due to these reasons, the resources have been suffering from lack of uniformity, heterogeneity as well as redundancy throughout the web. Ontologies have been widely used for solving such type of problems, as they help in extracting knowledge out of any information system. In this article, we focus on extracting concepts and their relations from a set of CSV files. These files are served as individual concepts and grouped into a particular domain, called the domain ontology. Furthermore, this domain ontology is used for capturing CSV data and represented in RDF format retaining links among files or concepts. Datatype and object properties are automatically detected from header fields. This reduces the task of user involvement in generating mapping files. The detail analysis has been performed on Baseball tabular data and the result shows a rich set of semantic information.

KEYWORDS

Ontology, Tabular Data, CSV, Semantic Web, RDF, Linked Data.

For More Details: <http://airccse.org/journal/ijwest/papers/6315ijwest06.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijwest/vol6.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] Han L, Finin T, Parr C, Sachs J and Joshi A, (2006) "[RDF123: a mechanism to transform spreadsheets to RDF](#)", Proceedings of the Twenty-First National Conference on Artificial Intelligence (AAAI), AAAI Press, Menlo Park.
- [2] Ermilov I, Auer S and Stadler C, (2013) "[Csv2rdf: User-driven csv to rdf mass conversion framework](#)", ISEM 13: 04-06.
- [3] Bizer C, Heath T, and Berners-Lee T, (2009) "[Linked data-the story so far](#)", International journal on semantic web and information systems 5.3: 1-22.
- [4] Taye MM, (2010) "[Understanding semantic web and ontologies: Theory and applications](#)", Journal of Computing 2 (6): 182-192.
- [5] Euzenat J, Le Bach T, Barrasa J, Bouquet P, De Bo J, Dieng R, Ehrig M, Hauswirth M, Jarrar M, Lara R, Maynard D, Napoli A, Stamou G, Stuckenschmidt H, Shvaiko P, Tessaris S, Van Acker S, and Zaihrayeu I, (2004) "D2. 2.3: State of the art on ontology alignment", Knowledge Web 2-3.
- [6] Uschold M and Gruninger M, (1996) "[Ontologies: Principles, methods and applications](#)", The knowledge engineering review 11.02: 93-136.
- [7] Lin J, Fox MS, and Bilgic T, (1996) "[A requirement ontology for engineering design](#)", Concurrent Engineering 4.3: 279-291.
- [8] Lee JH and Suh HW, (2008) "[Ontology-based multi-layered knowledge framework for product lifecycle management](#)", Concurrent Engineering 16.4: 301-311.
- [9] Dutra M, Ghodous P, Kuhn O and Tri NM, (2010) "[A generic and synchronous ontology-based architecture for collaborative design](#)", Concurrent Engineering 18 (1): 65-74.
- [10] Happel HJ, and Seedorf S, (2006) "[Applications of ontologies in software engineering](#)", Proc. Of Workshop on Semantic Web Enabled Software Engineering : 5-9.
- [11] Anantharangachar R, Ramani S, and Rajagopalan S, (2013) "[Ontology Guided Information Extraction from Unstructured Text](#)",
- [12] Lebo T and Williams GT, (2010) "[Converting governmental datasets into linked data](#)", Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Semantic Systems: 38.
- [13] Langegger A and Wöß W, (2009) "[XLWrap—querying and integrating arbitrary spreadsheets with SPARQL](#)", In: Springer Berlin Heidelberg. 8th International Semantic Web Conference. Chantilly, VA, USA, p. 359-374.
- [14] Mulwad V, Finin T and Joshi A, (2011) "[Automatically generating government linked data from tables](#)", Working notes of AAAI Fall Symposium on Open Government Knowledge: AI Opportunities and Challenges 4 (3).

- [15] Mulwad V, Finin T, Syed Z and Joshi A, (2010) "[Using Linked Data to Interpret Tables](#)", COLID 665.
- [16] Mulwad V, Finin T, Syed Z, and Joshi A, (2010) "[T2LD: Interpreting and Representing Tables as Linked Data](#)", In 9th International Semantic Web Conference ISWC : 25-28.
- [17] Spanos DE, Stavrou P and Mitrou N, (2012) "[Bringing relational databases into the semantic web: A survey](#)", Semantic Web 3 (2): 169-209.
- [18] Lin L, Xu Z and Ding Y, (2013) "[OWL Ontology Extraction from Relational Databases via Database Reverse Engineering](#)", Journal of Software 8 (11): 2749-2760.
- [19] Telnarova Z, (2010) "Relational database as a source of ontology creation", Computer Science and Information Technology (IMCSIT), Proceedings of the 2010 International Multiconference on IEEE: 135-139.
- [20] Dadjoo M and Kheirkhah E, (2015) "[An Approach For Transforming of Relational Databases to OWL Ontology](#)", International Journal of Web & Semantic Technology (IJWesT) Vol.6, No.1, January 2015.
- [21] Dimou A, Sande MV, Colpaert P, Verborgh R, Mannens E, and Walle RVd, (2014) "[RML: a generic language for integrated RDF mappings of heterogeneous data](#)", In Proceedings of the 7th Workshop on Linked Data on the Web.
- [22] Muñoz E, Hogan A and Mileo A, (2014) "[Using linked data to mine RDF from wikipedia's tables](#)", In Proceedings of the 7th ACM international conference on Web search and data mining: 533-542.
- [23] Petrou I, Meimaris M and Papastefanatos G, (2014) "[Towards a methodology for publishing Linked Open Statistical Data](#)", eJournal of eDemocracy & Open Government 6 (1).
- [24] Sharma K, Marjit U and Biswas U, (2014) "[Linking Library Data: A Linked Data Based Approach](#)", PLANNER – 2014, Capacity Building in Library and Information Services, Dibrugarh University, Assam (39).
- [25] Lange C, (2009) "[Krextor—an extensible XML→ RDF extraction framework](#)", Scripting and Development for the Semantic Web (SFSW) 449: 38.
- [26] Butler MH, Gilbert J, Seaborne A and Smathers K, (2004) "[Data conversion, extraction and record linkage using XML and RDF tools in Project SIMILE](#)", HP Labs, Bristol, UK.
- [27] Battle S, (2006) "Gloze: XML to RDF and back again", In Jena User Conference, May.: <http://jena.hpl.hp.com/juc2006/proceedings>
- [28] Sharma K, Marjit U and Biswas U, (2013) "[Exposing MARC 21 Format for Bibliographic Data As Linked Data With Provenance](#)", Journal of Library Metadata 13 (2-3): 212-229.
- [29] Lahman S, (2014) "Lahman's Baseball Database", In Baseball Archive: Dataset versions 2010- 2014. [Cited 2015 July 20]. Available from: <http://seanlahman.com/>

- [30] McBride B, (2001) "[Jena: Implementing the RDF Model and Syntax Specification](#)", In SemWeb.
- [31] Knublauch H, Fergerson RW, Noy NF and Musen MA, (2004) "[The Protégé OWL plugin: An open development environment for semantic web applications](#)", The Semantic Web–ISWC 2004, Springer Berlin Heidelberg: 29-243.
- [32] Alexander P, (2011) "Finding Ontologies", In The MMI Guides: Navigating the World of Marine Metadata. [Cited 2015 July 20]. Available from:<http://marinemetadata.org/guides/vocabs/ont/existing/finding>.

LOANONT-A RULE BASED ONTOLOGY FOR PERSONAL LOAN ELIGIBILITY EVALUATION

Neha Jain and Lalit Sen Sharma

Department of Computer Science and IT, University of Jammu, Jammu, India

ABSTRACT

In recent years, significant attention has been given to understand and implement banking solutions. The global competitive business environment and advancement in Information Technology and in particular internet technologies has facilitated the carrying out of banking activities outside the brick and mortar premise of the banks. Credit availing schemes are the core of the banking industry. Many agencies are working on it so as to make this facility hassle free for the customers and also to minimize the losses incurred by the banks in the form of bad debts. The challenge has been, and still is, to recognize, communicate and steadily improvise the banking solutions. The internet technologies are a potential candidates to overcome these challenges. The paper describes LoanOnt Ontology with the associated implementation toolset for creating an interoperable and sustainable personal loan calculation solution which would provide an intercommunication platform to facilitate integration and interoperation of information across interacting applications in banking scenarios.

KEYWORDS

Protégé, OWL (Web Ontology Language), SWRL(Semantic Web Rule Language), SQWRL(Semantic Query Enhanced-Web Rule Language).

For More Details: <http://airconline.com/ijwest/V7N4/7416ijwest02.pdf>

Volume Link: <http://www.airccse.org/journal/ijwest/vol7.html>

REFERENCES

- [1] World Wide Web consortium Web Ontology Language Reference manual <https://www.w3.org/2001/sw/wiki/OWL>
- [2] W3C OWL2 Reference Document https://www.w3.org/TR/2012/REC-owl2-overview20121211/#Documentation_Roadmap
- [3] Wikipedia Declarative Programming page https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Declarative_programming
- [4] W3C SWRL document <https://www.w3.org/Submission/SWRL/>
- [5] Connor O' Martin & Das Amar,(2009)"SQWRL: a Query Language for OWL", OWL: Experiences and Directions (OWLED), Fifth International Workshop
- [6] Wikipedia Ontology Language document: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ontology_language
- [7] P rotégé: <http://protege.stanford.edu/>
- [8] T. R. Gruber,(1993),"A Translation Approach to Portable Ontologies", Knowledge Acquisition, 5(2):199–220.
- [9] Ushold Mike&King Martin(1995),"Towards a Methodology for Building Ontologies", Workshop on Basic Ontological Issues in Knowledge Sharing, held in conjunction with IJCAI-95
- [10] Corcho, O., Fernandez-Lopez, M. & Gomez-Perez, A. (2003),"Methodologies, Tools and Languages for Building Ontologies: Where is their meeting point?", Data & Knowledge Engineering, 46: 41–64.
- [11] Baader, F., Calvanese, D., McGuinness, D.L., Nardi, D. and PatelSchneider, P.F.(2003), [The Description Logic Handbook: Theory, Implementation, and Applications](#), Cambridge University Press: Cambridge.
- [12] OWL API documentation : <http://owlapi.sourceforge.net/>
- [13] Jena Ontology API: <https://jena.apache.org/documentation/ontology/>